

***In Situ* FIBRILLATION OF LCP IN PC/PBT MATRIX**

Yang Leng, Dongfeng Zhao* and Ping Gao**

Department of Mechanical and **Department of Chemical Engineering
Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
Kowloon, Hong Kong

* Montell Hong Kong Technical Centre
Tai Po Industrial Estate, NT, Hong Kong

ABSTRACT

LCP, Vectra B950, reinforced polycarbonate (PC) 60 wt% /Polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) 40 wt% blends have been studied using injection moulding process. The composites with pre-blended matrix are made by blending PC and PBT in a twin screw extruder, and then by injection moulding with LCP. Good *in situ* fibrillation of LCP is observed in the directly injection moulded LCP composites. The fibrillation of LCP appears to follow Taylor's droplet deformation theory. Results indicate that addition of PBT improves the skin-core distribution of LCP fibrils in the matrix and also improves the adhesion between the matrix and Vectra B950 which contains terephthalic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Composites of liquid crystalline polymers (LCPs) and thermoplastics have attracted much research attention recently, because high strength LCPs can form *in situ* fibrils to reinforce thermoplastics during extrusion and injection moulding. Differing from glass fiber reinforcement, LCPs also serve as processing aids in extrusion and injection moulding due to their low melt viscosity.

In order to efficiently reinforce thermoplastics matrix, long, well oriented and uniformly distributed fibrils of LCP should be formed during processing, and also good interfacial bonding must be achieved. Spherical LCP droplets, however, instead of fibrils often observed in the LCP composites are due to poor processing. A skin-core effect has regularly been observed in injection-moulded LCP composites [1]; a high concentration of well formed fibrils align in the skin region, but poor fibrils and particulate LCP remain in the core region. Commonly LCP and thermoplastics are highly immiscible, thus high interfacial tension results in poor interfacial bonding.

In this work Vectra B950 LCP is used to reinforce a blended matrix of polycarbonate (PC) and Polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) in order to achieve improved morphology and

mechanical behavior of the LCP composites. Rigid-rigid PBT/PC polymer blends have received considerable attention because of their good mechanical properties, chemical resistance and temperature tolerance. The rationale of using PC/PBT blends as a matrix for LCP composites is to take advantages of both the aforementioned characteristics of PBT/PC and the better compatibility between LCP and PBT because the Vectra B950 LCP used in this work contains terephthalic acid. We believe that using an alloyed matrix in polymer composites could have synergistic effects as significant as those derived from using alloyed matrices in metal matrix composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polycarbonate (Calibre 300-15) used in this work was provided by Dow Chemical. The Polybutylene terephthalate (Valox 325) was supplied by General Electric Plastic Co, and the LCP (Vectra B950) came from Hoechst-Celanese. Vectra B950 is a wholly aromatic liquid-crystal poly(ester-co-amide) composed of 58 mol (%) hydroxynaphthoic acid, 21 mol (%) terephthalic acid and 21 mol (%) of para-aminophenol.

PC and PBT were blended in a twin screw extruder, and then injection moulded with LCP pellets. We chose a PC/PBT matrix with weight ratio of 60 to 40 which exhibits a good combination of strength and toughness [2]. For comparison, tensile bars of PC, PBT, and Vectra B950 LCP, as well as PC/LCP composites were made using direct injection moulding.

Injection moulding experiments were carried out in a reciprocating screw injection moulding machine (Minijet 20D, Chen Hsong Co., Hong Kong) with a clamping force of 20 t and a maximum shot weight of 28 g. The operation conditions used for LCP composites were: injection temperature 290 °C, mould temperature 70 °C, injection time 5 s, injection pressure 85 bars, holding pressure 40 bars, and holding time 15 s.

An injection mould of a tensile bar was used and the injection gate located at the end of the bar. Pre-blending of PC and PBT was carried out on a (BTS30, BETOL Co.) twin screw extruder with a screw speed of 20 rpm. All polymer resins were dried in an oven at 120 °C for at least 24 hours before extrusion and injection moulding.

Morphology of the LCP composites was examined using a JEOL Scanning Electron Microscope (JSM-6300F). After grinding and polishing, the samples were etched with diethylenetriamine that dissolves PC in order to reveal LCP fibrils and PBT microstructure. The samples were sputter-coated with gold before SEM examinations.

Wide angle X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained using a flat film camera and Mo radiation at 25 mA and 50 KV. The X-ray beam was made monochromatic by using a nickel filter to give a wavelength of 0.7 nm. Observations were made on both pure injection moulded LCP and the LCP extracted from the PC/LCP blend. The LCP fibre extraction from the PC/LCP blend was achieved by dissolving the blend by dichloromethane at 39 °C and the remaining LCP fibres within the blend matrix was mounted on the X-ray diffractometer. The exposure time for LCP fibres within the blend and pure LCP was 40 and 12 minutes, respectively.

Rheological properties of PC, PBT, PC/PBT, and Vectra LCP samples were measured using the Goffert Capillary rheometer 2003A. Prior to all measurements, samples were dried in the vacuum oven at 80 C for 12 hours. A slit capillary die of 1 mm thickness and 15 mm width and 300 mm length was used. All measurements were carried out at 290 °C.

Tensile moduli of the injected moulded tensile bars were measured according to ASTM standard D638M-87B using a SINTECH tensile testing machine. The sample size was 3 mm thick, 12.7 mm wide and 100 mm long in the reduced section. The strain was measured with an extensometer with 25 mm gage length. The crosshead speed was 10 mm/min. The arithmetic average and the standard deviation of measurements were calculated using a minimum of five samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MORPHOLOGY OF LCP

The SEM micrographs of composite longitudinal sections (Fig. 1) reveal LCP morphology and distributions in the PC and PC/PBT matrices. Figure 1 shows the half-thickness sections of the injected tensile bars of binary PC/LCP and ternary PC/PBT/LCP systems. Thirty weight percent Vectra B950 provides a large number of fibrils along the flow direction in the composites. Impressively, the aspect ratios of Vectra B950 fibrils in these injection moulded composites are very large, the majority being almost continuous fibres. On the other hand, the skin-core phenomenon occurs in both systems: many LCP fibrils align along the flow direction near the skin area; fewer fibrils exist near the core. Also the fibril size varies from the skin to core. In the core region spherical droplets of LCP can be seen from the higher magnification micrographs of both systems.

Figure 1 also reveals that the skin-core effect is more severe in PC/LCP than in PC/PBT/LCP in which more fibrils are formed near the core. This indicates that addition of PBT to the matrix improves fibrillation and distribution of Vectra B950 in the injection-moulded composites. The PBT forms randomly orientated micro-fibrils ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameters) in the PC/PBT/LCP blends, and can be identified by the contrast and size differences from the LCP fibrils in the SEM micrograph (Fig. 2). More details of PBT morphology in the blended systems is given in ref. [3].

FIBRILLATION

Fibrillation of LCP in thermoplastics is rather complex in rheology and chemistry. No existing theories can be directly applied to LCP fibrillation that involves deformation of a non-Newtonian melt. The essence of Taylor's theory on the deformation of Newtonian droplets suspended in another Newtonian fluid, however, can be adopted: deformation of melt droplets depends on competition between the applied force on the droplets and interfacial tension between droplets and surrounding flows [4]. For an applied shear stress, such competition is represented by the capillary number (κ). Also the theory indicates the deformation is a function of viscosity ratio between droplets and matrix (λ).

$$\kappa = \eta_m \dot{\gamma} a / \sigma \quad \lambda = \eta_d / \eta_m \quad (1)$$

where η_m and η_d are the viscosity of matrix and droplet respectively, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate, σ the interfacial tension and a the diameter of droplet. High κ value is desirable for fibrillation of dispersed LCP phase in the melt. Effect of λ is not very clear. It has been reported that λ is important in shear flow, but much less important in elongational flow [5].

Apparent shear viscosity versus shear rate for PC, PBT, LCP and PC/PBT blend is shown in

Fig. 3. At the injection temperature (290°C), PC shows the highest viscosity and it is almost Newtonian. The Vectra LCP shows a power law shear thinning behaviour and its melt viscosity lies between PBT and PC. The binary blend of PC/PBT blend shows the lowest viscosity. The nearly Newtonian behavior observed on PBT and PC/PBT is due to the high temperature of measurement. The viscosity ratios for LCP/PC and LCP/(PC/PBT) are 0.4 and 2.5 respectively, at 100 1/s. Under all frequency tested, the viscosity ratio, λ , for the ternary blend is much higher than that of the binary blend.

Interfacial tension of the blends has not been directly measured. The preliminary DSC results, however, indicate possible transesterification during the process of the ternary blend (further study with DSC and FTIR will be conducted). The chemical affinity of PBT and Vectra B950 can promote interaction between them. We reason that the presence of PBT acts as a compatibilizer between the matrix and LCP. This would have resulted in a substantial decrease of interfacial tension. Lower interfacial tension between LCP and PC/PBT matrix is also evidenced by better interface adhesion in the ternary system than in the binary system. Figure 4 indicates interfacial bonding in the LCP composites. The micrographs of fracture surfaces clearly reveal that the interface between the LCP fibrils and the PC matrix are separated (Fig. 4a), but such debonding is not seen between the LCP fibrils and the PC/PBT matrix (Fig. 4b).

Figure 1 indicates that the level of fibrillation is similar in both the systems, but the ternary one shows a better fibrillation and fibril distribution. We believe such a fibrillation feature results from the lower interfacial tension of the ternary blend due to the addition of PBT.

There is uncertainty about the stress field responsible for LCP fibrillation, whether the fibrillation results from shear flows or elongational flows. It is believed that elongation flow exists in injection moulding due to a fountain effect at the flow front. The mouse-like LCP droplets in the SEM micrograph of the LCP composite provide evidence of fibrillation due to elongational flow (Fig. 5). Elongation flow during moulding may explain the apparent insensitivity of the fibrillation to the viscosity ratio. Figure 5 also shows that the sizes of most undeformed LCP droplets are small ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$). This micrograph confirms that the fibrillation is strongly droplet size-dependent, consistent with the Taylor theory in that the smaller the droplet diameter, the less chance for the droplet to be fibrillated.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

Stiffness of injection-moulded LCP composites is superior to PC and PBT as indicated in Fig. 6a. For example, 30 wt % of LCP content exhibits a tensile modulus of 8.1 GPa, more than three times higher than that of PC (2.3 GPa). The moduli of the ternary LCP composites are distinctly higher than those of PC/LCP composites when LCP content is more than 10%. The Tsai-halpin equation is widely used to predict the modulus of discontinuously reinforced composites [6]. When fibers become continuous and perfectly align along the load direction, the composite tensile modulus (E_c) can be predicted by the simple rule of mixtures (ROM):

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f) \quad (2)$$

where subscripts m and f of modulus (E) and volume fraction (V) represent the matrix and fiber respectively. Figure 6b shows comparison of the measured composite moduli with prediction from the rule of mixtures. The LCP composite systems follow ROM quite well even though LCP fibrils do not quite provide continuous reinforcement in the system.

Theoretically, the rule of mixtures should not describe the moduli of the LCP *in situ* composites due to the following reasons: the LCP is not totally fibrillated (Fig. 5) in the thermoplastics matrix; the fibrils are not perfectly aligned in the longitudinal direction of

the tensile bars; and the aspect ratios vary even though the majority are larger than 40. Furthermore, the adhesion between LCP and the thermoplastics is far from perfect. Note that the modulus value of pure LCP (21.3 GPa) in Fig. 6b was measured from the directly injected Vectra B950 tensile bars. Note that the tensile modulus of LCP fibrils varies with crystal orientation in the fibrils. It has been reported that the modulus of Vectra B with perfect crystal orientation along the tensile axis should be about 100 GPa [7,8]. The LCP crystal orientation along the tensile axis is revealed by the patterns of wide angle X-ray diffraction (Fig. 7). The equatorial distribution of diffraction in Fig. 7 corresponds to the interchain correlation of LCP. Fig. 7 shows that the intensity peak in equatorial direction is sharper in the blends than in the pure LCP bar. It indicates that LCP fibrils extracted from the blends exhibit better crystal orientation along the tensile axis than that of pure LCP bars. We attribute the good crystal orientation in the blends to their high percentage of fibrils well oriented near skin. We observed that the fibrils in the core of the pure LCP bars are not well aligned in the tensile direction. Thus the average orientation of LCP fibrils in the LCP tensile bars is not as good as in the blends.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Addition of PBT to a PC matrix improves the distribution of Vectra B950 in composites and improves the interfacial bonding due to better compatibility between PBT and Vectra B950. The fibrillation of LCP in PC/PBT blends shows consistent agreement with the Taylor's theory of droplet deformation.
2. LCP *in situ* composites of high stiffness can be made by direct injection moulding of LCP pellets with PC and PBT when processing is appropriately controlled. The LCP crystals in the injection moulded composite bars exhibit better orientation along the injection direction than in the injected moulded pure LCP bars. This phenomenon explains the apparent good fit of the rule of mixtures to the experimental data.

REFERENCES

1. A. Valenza, F. P. La Mantia, M. Paci and P. L. Magagnini, *Intern. Polym. Process.* **4**, 247 (1991).
2. J. S. Wu, A. F. Yee and Y. W. Mai, *J. of Mat. Sci.*, **29**, 4510 (1994).
3. Q. W. Xu, Y. Leng and Y. W. Mai, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, to be published.
4. G. I. Taylor, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser-A*, **146**, 501 (1934).
5. R. A. De Bruijn, PhD thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands (1989).
6. J. C. Halpin and J. L. Kardos, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, **16**, 344 (1976).
7. H. Zhang, G. R. Davies, and I. M. Ward, *Polymer*, **33**, 2651 (1992).
8. Q. Lin and A. F. Yee, *Polym. Composites*, **15**, 156 (1994).

Fig. 1 SEM micrographs of the LCP composites in flow directions. a) PC/LCP, b) PC/PBT/LCP. The LCP fibril distributions from skin to core are revealed.

Fig. 2 SEM micrograph of PC/PBT/LCP indicates that PBT microfibrils randomly orientate and tangle with large LCP fibrils.

Fig. 3 Viscosity as a function of shear rates at 290°C.

Fig. 4 Difference of interfacial bonding between matrix and LCP is revealed from the fractography of PC/LCP (a) and PC/PBT/LCP (b).

Fig. 5 Partial fibrillated and unfibrillated LCP droplets in PC/LCP.

Fig. 6 (a) Tensile moduli of LCP composites as a function of LCP content. (b) Comparison of tensile modulus of PC/PBT/LCP and the ROM prediction.

Fig. 7 X-ray diffraction patterns of the LCP crystals in tensile bars. (a) pure LCP, (b) PC/30 wt% LCP. The equatorial distribution represents their variation of crystal orientation.